

Micro-Raman and SEM-EDS analyses to evaluate the nature of salts-cluster particles present in Secondary Marine Aerosol

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ABSTRACT

Marine aerosol is a complex inorganic and organic chemistry system which contains several salts, mainly forming different type of salt clusters. Different environmental parameters have a key role in their formation of these aggregates. The relative humidity (%RH), temperature, CO, SO₂ and NO_x levels and even the O₃ levels (reduction and oxidation) can promote different chemical reactions giving rise to salt clusters with different morphology and sizes. Sulfates, nitrates and chlorides and even chlorosulfates or nitrosulfates are the final compounds which can be found in environments with a direct influence of marine aerosol. In order to collect and analyze these types of compounds, the use of adequate samplers is crucial. In this work, salt-cluster particles were collected thanks to the use of a self-made passive sampler (SMPS) settled in a 20th century historic building (Punta Begoña Galleries, Getxo, Basque Country, Spain) which is surrounded by a beach and a sportive port. These salt-clusters were finally analyzed directly by Raman micro-spectroscopy and scanning electron microscope coupled to an energy dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (SEM-EDS).

Keywords: marine aerosol, port environment, Raman spectroscopy, SEM-EDS, dry deposition.

40 **1. Introduction**

41 Marine aerosol constitutes one of the most important natural aerosols from the Earth. It
42 contributes significantly to the Earth's radioactive budget, biogeochemical cycling and
43 even to air quality. Marine aerosol comprises primary and secondary aerosol
44 components. The primary marine aerosol (PMA) is formed due to the interaction of
45 wind with the ocean surface. The result of this interaction is the mechanical production
46 of sea spray (inorganic sea salts and organic matter). Sea spray is produced when the
47 bubbles from the generated whitecap burst. This process originates a jet of saline drops
48 commonly known as sea spray aerosol (SSA). This aerosol carries particles of
49 submicrometre size up to a few micrometres (Rodriguez-Navarro et al., 1999). It is
50 estimated that whitecap formation occurs when the wind reaches the speed of $4\text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$.
51 One of the physical characteristics of the sea aerosol is the size of its suspended
52 particles ($>1\ \mu\text{m}$), which depends on the wind speed, sea-air water transfer, etc.
53 (O'Dowd and de Leeuw 2007). The global annual mass emission of primary marine
54 particles (PMP), or sea aerosol, is estimated to range from $2\cdot 10^{12}$ to $1\cdot 10^{14}$ $\text{Kg}\cdot\text{year}^{-1}$,
55 which is comparable to that of dust aerosol (Textor et al., 2006). Apart from this, the
56 SSA has a key role in chemical reactions such as the coupled cycles of sulfate-sea salt
57 (O'Dowd et al., 1999a; 2000) and nitric acid-sea salt (Sørensen et al., 2005). Apart from
58 that, other authors focused their attention in the study of SSA role in the climate change
59 (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) In Climate change, 2001). SSA
60 has also been linked to the *marine* boundary layer (MBL) cycle through the activation
61 of halogens, leading to ozone depletion (O'Dowd et al., 1999b; Vogt et al., 1996;
62 McFiggens et al., 2000).

63 The secondary marine aerosol (SMA) production consists on cluster particle formation
64 resulting from gas to solid particle conversion (O'Dowd and de Leeuw 2007). The
65 sulfur species present in the atmosphere and coming from the anthropogenic emissions
66 are closely related with the SMA formation. The SMA formation occurs in two steps.
67 The first step consists in the new particle formation via the nucleation of 0.5–1 nm
68 stable clusters. Once these clusters are formed, they can grow to larger sizes via
69 condensation. The second step consists in the clusters growing via different
70 heterogeneous reactions and aqueous phase oxidation of dissolved gases in existing
71 aerosol particles. In terms of the sulfur cycle, dimethylsulphide (DMS), a waste
72 produced by phytoplankton, is released from the ocean into the atmosphere where it

73 undergoes oxidation by the OH radical to form SO₂, which is further oxidized to H₂SO₄
74 (Charlson et al., 1987). H₂SO₄ is thought to participate in binary homogeneous
75 nucleation with H₂O, and in ternary nucleation with H₂O and NH₃. Apart from this, in
76 coastal zones where regular and significant particle nucleation takes place, iodine oxides
77 have a key role in clusters nucleations and growth (O'Dowd et al., 2002).

78 According to the different sizes that aerosol particles can raise, marine aerosol clusters
79 can have 1000-10000 nm volume diameter size (Heitzenberg et al., 2003).

80 Although the main mass fraction of marine aerosol is inorganic sea salts, organic matter
81 is also present and can contribute to the overall mass (Claeys et al., 2010). Usually,
82 marine aerosol carries organic residues from the decomposition of algae, plankton and
83 salts. The most abundant salt carried on marine aerosol is sodium chloride, but other
84 types of chemical compounds like sulfates and nitrates can be also present (Zhao and
85 Gao, 2008; Abdalmogith et al., 2006).

86 Apart from chlorides, sulfates and nitrates, other ions are also present in a suspended
87 way such as Ca²⁺, K⁺, Mg²⁺, Fe³⁺, Al³⁺, Sr²⁺, NH₄⁺, HCO₃⁻ and Br⁻. Usually, organic
88 matter has also high importance because it represents around the 10% of marine aerosol
89 (Chameides and Stelson, 1992; Tervahattu et al., 2005). Additionally, P.M._{2.5} and
90 P.M.₁₀ airborne particulate matter can be transported by the marine aerosol including
91 metals such as Pb, Cd, Cr, Mn, Cu, Mo, Rh, Ni, As, Ti, V and Hg (Calparsoro et al.,
92 2017; Arruti et al., 2011; Morillas et al., 2016a; 2016b). The source of these heavy
93 metals can reside in the influence of maritime traffic, port activities and also industry or
94 even road traffic (Gómez et al., 2005).

95 Taking into account the high amount of cluster-salts present in marine aerosol, it is clear
96 that this environmental factor has influence on the surrounding landscape. One of this is
97 the surrounding built heritage. In this sense, there are many chemical reactions involved
98 in the interaction between marine aerosol and building materials (García-Florentino et
99 al. 2016; Morillas et al. 2012; 2013; 2015a; 2016c; 2016d).

100 In this work, a marine cluster salts study based on the use of Raman micro-spectroscopy
101 and SEM-EDS was carried out. Thanks to the use of self-made passive sampler (SMPS)
102 settled in a 20th century historic building (Punta Begoña Galleries, Getxo, Basque
103 Country, Spain), which is surrounded by a beach and a sportive port, the salt-clusters

104 were collected. Moreover, in order to correlate the nature of some cluster salts, different
105 environmental parameters (RH%, T°(°C), CO, O₃, SO_x and NO_x) were extracted from
106 Basque Government environmental station which is located close to the sportive port.

107

108 **2. Materials and methods**

109 *2.1 Self-made passive sampler (SMPS)*

110 The passive sampler design used and successfully tested in the Punta Begoña Galleries
111 has been previously described elsewhere (Morillas et al., 2016a). This passive sampler
112 basically consists in a polystyrene cylinder where several pins stubs covered with
113 carbon tapes are inserted inside. Thanks to the natural wind and the nature of the tapes,
114 many different types of suspended particles can be deposited (see Figure 1). The content
115 of the "pin stubs", mainly particulate material adhered to it, can be characterized
116 directly without any pretreatment in the laboratory, which can be considered one of the
117 greater advantages of this sampler, comparing to other systems of particulate matter
118 sampling

119 *2.2 Climate conditions*

120 Thanks to the Basque Government environmental station which is located close to the
121 sportive port, different environmental parameters were extracted (see Figure S1 from
122 Supplementary Material). As it can be seen, the high levels of NO_x and SO₂ during the
123 autumn and winter helped us to decide the best sampling period (from November to
124 February) in order to collect the highest amount of salt-clusters.

125 *2.3 Instrumentation*

126 The SEM-EDS analyses were carried out using an EVO[®]40 Scanning Electron
127 Microscope (Carl Zeiss NTS GmbH, Germany) coupled to a X-Max Energy-Dispersive
128 X-ray spectrometer (Oxford Instruments, Abingdon, Oxfordshire, United Kingdom) for
129 electron image acquisitions and elemental analysis (punctual and imaging). Although
130 sometimes, deposited particles alone are not conductive, it was possible to obtain
131 optimal results without coating the samples. SEM images were obtained at high vacuum
132 employing an acceleration voltage of 30 kV and a 10 to 400 µm working distance.

133 Different magnifications (reaching up to $\times 6800$) were used for secondary electron
134 images and an integration time of 50 s was employed to improve the signal-to-noise
135 ratio. The EDS spectra were acquired and treated using the INCA software.
136 Furthermore, a map acquisition of specific microscopic areas in the samples was also
137 performed, allowing the evaluation of the distribution of these elements throughout the
138 sample.

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140 For the micro-Raman analyses, the inVia Renishaw confocal Raman microspectrometer
141 (Renishaw, Gloucestershire, UK) coupled to a DMLM Leica microscope with 5 \times , 20 \times ,
142 50 \times , and 100 \times long working distance lens was used. Excitation laser (514 nm; nominal
143 laser power 350 mW and 50 mW, respectively) and different magnification lenses (50 \times
144 and 100 \times , mainly) were used to perform the measurements. The spectrometer was daily
145 calibrated by using the 520 cm^{-1} Raman band of a silicon chip. Lasers were set at low
146 power (not more than 1 mW at the sample) in order to avoid sample decomposition.
147 Data acquisition was carried out using the Wire 3.2 software package (Renishaw).
148 Spectra were acquired between 100 and 3000 cm^{-1} and several scans (between 10-40
149 scans) were accumulated for each spectrum in order to improve the signal-to-noise ratio.
150 The interpretation of all the Raman results was performed by comparison of the
151 acquired Raman spectra with Raman spectra of pure standard compounds collected in
152 the e-VISNICH dispersive Raman database (Maguregui et al., 2010). Additionally, free
153 Raman databases (e.g. RRUFF (Downs and Hall-Wallace, 2002)) were also considered
154 for the assignation of Raman bands.

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157 **3. Results and Discussion**

158 As mentioned above, the location of the Punta Begoña Galleries makes the façade to be
159 exposed to all types of atmospheric conditions. In this sense, the favorable direction of
160 the winds to the façade is a determining factor in the deposition of the particles. It
161 should also be noted that the presence of the marine aerosol also influences on the
162 composition of the set of suspended particles and cluster salts, which in turn have a
163 negative influence on the durability of the materials.

164 *3.1 SEM-EDS analyses*

165 The results obtained by SEM-EDS indicated the presence of salts with different
166 elemental composition. Indeed, as shown in Figure 2, different acquired mappings and
167 subsequently their elemental distribution is presented in the cluster salt itself. Usually,
168 the elemental base is Halite (NaCl) and around of this, different particles can be
169 observed in which their composition can vary (see Figure 2A, 2B, 2C and 2D). Thus, as
170 can be seen in Figures 2A and 2B, the elemental composition of Ca, S and O could be
171 related to the presence of calcium sulfates (anhydrite (CaSO_4) and/or gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot$
172 $2\text{H}_2\text{O}$)). Additionally, other elements such as Mg, K, and Si may be also related to the
173 presence of aluminosilicates and other types of sulfates such as magnesium sulfates
174 (epsomite ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and hexahydrate ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$)). Moreover, as shown in
175 Figure 2C, other elements such as nitrogen are also present, which may be related to the
176 presence of nitrates coupled to halite particles. The fact that these particles are present
177 in this environment demonstrates how aggressive the environment is for the
178 conservation of the Galleries under study. On the other hand, the presence of other
179 additional elements such as phosphorus and fluor was observed (see Figure 2D), which
180 would be directly related to the presence of phosphate compounds which are in the
181 environment and easily coupled to these halite particles. Finally, the presence of fluor
182 could be related with the presence of fluorides, compounds that are usually present in the
183 marine aerosol. All of these compounds as it has been pointed out above, have a
184 degradation effect on building materials, causing the formation of salts and over time
185 promoting loss of material.

186 In many cases, different salts present in the atmosphere react with other salts giving rise
187 to new compounds that can grow till larger sizes depending on the different atmospheric
188 conditions. Temperature, pressure and relative humidity (% RH) play a key role in this
189 type of reactions. Thus, during time, these salts can grow giving rise to clusters of salts
190 that can react with the building material through dry deposition, promoting reactions on
191 the material itself, and causing over time the loss of material. As an example, in Figure
192 3, the process of formation of a mixed sulfate (NaCaClSO_4) can be observed. In this
193 way, through reactions between halite (NaCl, the most common salt in the marine
194 aerosol) (Figure 3A) together with anhydrite (CaSO_4) (Figure 3B) also present in the sea
195 salt can lead to the complex NaCaClSO_4 (Figure 3D). This reaction process has been
196 observed in the Punta Begoña SMPS. In addition, it was possible to be observe in an
197 intermediate step how the halite and anhydrite particles are mixed together to form that

198 complex (Figure 3C). In the following reactions (1-3) the possible formation of the
199 NaCaClSO₄ is presented.

203 In addition, as it can be seen in Figure 4, cluster salts such as glauberite (Na₂Ca(SO₄)₂)
204 were also identified in the marine aerosol, which appeared in the Punta Begoña
205 Galleries sampling point with great assiduity (Figure 4A). Thus, related with this
206 compound and as shown in Figure 4B, different particles composed by aluminosilicates
207 and iron oxides can be added to glauberite, increasing its cluster salt diameter size (up to
208 60 μm). In the same way, halite particles and other conglomerates such as iron oxides
209 and aluminosilicates can be coupled together, forming consequently more complex
210 compounds or clusters (Figure 4C).

211 *3.2 Raman spectroscopy analyses*

212 To complement the elemental information obtained by SEM-EDS, Raman analyses of
213 the salts deposited in the pins placed in the Punta Begoña Galleries were directly carried
214 out, in where the molecular composition of these salts clusters was obtained. Micro-
215 Raman spectroscopy revealed the presence of many cluster salts, which during time can
216 react with the Punta Begoña Galleries materials by dry deposition, giving rise to
217 different decay processes that can promote loss of material. In general way, a summary
218 table of the main salts-clusters detected by Raman spectroscopy is presented (see Table
219 1). As it can be observed in Table 1, the great majority of the compounds identified
220 corresponds to sulfates, which corroborates the observed results obtained by SEM-EDS,
221 where magnesium sulfates (hexahydrate, epsomite), calcium sulfates (anhydrite and
222 gypsum), as well as all kinds of mixed and complex sulfates such as eugsterite,
223 syngenite, polyhalite and glauberite were also observed. In addition to this massive
224 presence of sulfates, the presence of nitrates such as nitratine and mixed compounds
225 such as darapskite are also observed. In this case as explained above, sulfates and
226 nitrates have a degrading effect on the materials.

227 Moreover, as example, different Raman spectra of these clusters are also presented in
228 the Figure 5. In this way, mascagnite ($(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$), main raman band at 974 cm^{-1})
229 (Morillas et al., 2015b) (Figure 5A), nitratine (NaNO_3 , main raman band at 1067 cm^{-1})
230 (Morillas et al., 2016e) (Figure 5B), epsomite ($\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, main raman band at 985
231 cm^{-1}) (Figure 5C) and syngenite ($\text{K}_2\text{Ca}(\text{SO}_4) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$) (Morillas et al., 2015b) main
232 raman bands at 981 and 1006 cm^{-1}) (Figure 5D) were observed. Other cluster salts such
233 as niter (KNO_3), glauberite ($\text{CaNa}_2(\text{SO}_4)_2$), anhydrite (CaSO_4) and hexahydrate (MgSO_4
234 $\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were also observed.

235 **4. Conclusions**

236 The combined analytical methodology used in this work using SEM-EDS (point by
237 point and imaging) and Raman spectroscopy has been proved as a powerful analytical
238 strategy to characterize the composition of different salt-clusters particles from the
239 SMA. The different climatic conditions (%RH, T° , CO, O_3 , NO_x and SO_2) showed that
240 the period from November to February () is the best one to perform the sampling due to
241 higher levels of NO_x and SO_2 . The SMPS presented in this work has been proved as a
242 powerful, cheap and efficient system that helped us to characterize the different cluster
243 salts present in marine aerosol and that can be deposited on the surface of building
244 materials by dry deposition process. The deposited particles can react with Built
245 Heritage material, promoting the formation of deterioration products that during time
246 jeopardize the loss of material in the building. Finally, in this work, the influence of
247 marine aerosol in the conservation state of historical buildings has been demonstrated,
248 where these particles such as sulfates and nitrates cannot be only formed in the building
249 material following a reaction between the carbonate from the material itself and the acid
250 aerosols deposited following wet deposition, but also by the inclusion of salts coming
251 from water infiltrations, as it has been described in the literature many times. The
252 sulfate, nitrate and chloride salts can also be present in the material as deposited
253 airborne particulate matter following dry deposition.

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257 **Acknowledgements**

258 This work has been funded by the Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness and the
259 European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) through the project DISILICA-1930
260 (ref. BIA2014-59124-P) and by the cooperation agreement between the University of
261 the Basque Country (UPV/EHU) and the City Council of Getxo (OTRI2014-0639).
262 Technical support provided by General X-ray Service of the SGIKER (UPV/EHU,
263 Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness of Spain, Basque Government, ERDF and
264 European Social Fund) is also gratefully acknowledged.

265 **References**

266 Abdalmogith, S.S., Harrison, R.M., Derwent, R.G., 2006. Particulate sulphate and
267 nitrate in Southern England and Northern Ireland during 2002/3 and its formation in a
268 photochemical trajectory mode, *Science of the Total Environment*. 368, 769-780.

269 Arruti, A., Fernandez-Olmo, I., Irabien, A., 2011. Regional evaluation of particulate
270 matter composition in an Atlantic coastal area (Cantabria region, northern Spain):
271 Spatial variations in different urban and rural environments, *Atmospheric Research*.
272 101, 280-293.

273 Calparsoro, E., Maguregui, M., Giakoumaki, A., Morillas, H., Madariaga, J.M., 2017.
274 Evaluation of black crust formation and soiling process on historical buildings from the
275 Bilbao metropolitan area (north of Spain) using SEM-EDS and Raman microscopy,
276 *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 24, 9468–9480.

277 Chameides, W.L., Stelson, A.W., 1992. Aqueous-phase chemical processes in
278 deliquescent sea salt aerosols: A mechanism that couples the atmospheric cycles of S
279 and sea salts, *Journal of Geophysical Research*. 97, 565-580.

280 Charlson, R.J., Lovelock, J.E., Andreae, M.O., Warren, S.G., 1987. Oceanic
281 phytoplankton, atmospheric sulfur, cloud albedo and climate, *Nature*. 326, 655–661.

282 Claeys, M., Wang, W., Vermeylen, R., Kourtchev, I., Chi, X., Farhat, Y., Surratt, J.D.,
283 Gómez-González, Y., Sciare, J., Maenhaut, W., 2010. Chemical characterisation of

284 marine aerosol at Amsterdam Island during the austral summer of 2006–2007, *Journal*
285 *of Aerosol Science*. 41, 13-22

286 Downs, R.T., Hall-Wallace, M., 2002. A database of crystal structures published in the
287 *American mineralogist* and the *Canadian mineralogist* and its use as a resource in the
288 classroom. 18th General Meeting of the International Mineralogical Association, p. 128.

289 García-Florentino, C., Maguregui, M., Morillas, H., Balziskueta, U., Azcarate, A.,
290 Arana, G., Madariaga, J.M., 2016. Portable and Raman imaging usefulness to detect
291 decaying on mortars from Punta Begoña Galleries (Getxo, North of Spain), *J. Raman*
292 *Spectrosc.* 47, 1458–1466.

293 Gómez, E.T., Sanfeliu, T., Rius, J., Jordan, M.M., 2005. Evolution, Sources and
294 Distribution of Mineral Particles and Amorphous Phase of Atmospheric Aerosol in An
295 Industrial and Mediterranean Coastal Area, *Water Air & Soil Pollution*. 167, 311-330.

296 Heintzenberg, J., Raes, F., Schwartz, S., *Atmospheric Chemistry in a Changing World*,
297 Chapter 4. Tropospheric Aerosols, Springer-Verlag, New York, USA, (2003).

298 Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) In *Climate change 2001: the*
299 *scientific basis* (eds J. T. Houghton, Y. Ding, D. J. Griggs, M. Noguer, P. J. van der
300 Linden & D. Xiaosu), Cambridge University Press, New York, USA, 2001.

301 Maguregui, M., Prieto-Taboada, N., Trebolazabala, J., Goienaga, N., Arrieta, N.,
302 Aramendia, J., Gomez-Nubla, L., Sarmiento, A., Olivares, M., Carrero, J.A., Martinez-
303 Arkarazo, I., Castro, K., Arana, G., Olazabal, M.A., Fernandez, L.A., Madariaga, J.M.,
304 2010. CHEMCH 1st International Congress Chemistry for Cultural Heritage, Ravenna,
305 30th June–3rd July.

306 McFiggens, G., Plane, J.M.C., Allan, B.J., Carpenter, L.J., Coe, H., O’Dowd, C.D.,
307 2000. A model study of Iodine chemistry in the marine boundary layer, *Journal of*
308 *Geophysical Research*. 105, 14371-14386.

309 Morillas, H., Maguregui, M., Gómez-Laserna, O., Trebolazabala, J., Madariaga, J.M.,
310 2012. Characterisation and diagnosis of the conservation state of cementitious materials
311 exposed to the open air in XIX century lighthouses located on the coast of the Basque

312 Country: “the case of Igueldo lighthouse, San Sebastian, North of Spain”. *J. Raman*
313 *Spectrosc.* 43, 1630–1636.

314 Morillas, H., Maguregui, M., Gómez-Laserna, O., Trebolazabala, J., Madariaga, J.M.,
315 2013. Could marine aerosol contribute to deteriorate building materials from interior
316 areas of lighthouses? An answer from the analytical chemistry point of view. *J. Raman*
317 *Spectrosc.* 44, 1700–1710.

318 Morillas, H., Maguregui, M., Paris, C., Bellot-Gurlet, L., Colomban, P., Madariaga,
319 J.M., 2015a. The role of marine aerosol in the formation of (double) sulphate/nitrate
320 salts in plasters. *Microchem. J.* 123, 148–157.

321 Morillas, H., Maguregui, M., Trebolazabala, J., Madariaga, J.M., 2015b. Nature and
322 origin of white efflorescence on bricks, artificial stones, and joint mortars of modern
323 houses evaluated by portable Raman spectroscopy and laboratory analyses.
324 *Spectrochim. Acta A-M.* 136, 1195–1203.

325 Morillas, H., Maguregui, M., García-Florentino, C., Marcaida, I., Madariaga, J.M.,
326 2016a. Study of particulate matter from Primary/Secondary Marine Aerosol and
327 anthropogenic sources collected by a self-made passive sampler for the evaluation of the
328 dry deposition impact on Built Heritage, *Sci. Total Environ.* 550, 285-296.

329 Morillas, H., Maguregui, M., García-Florentino, C., Carrero, J.A., Salcedo, I.,
330 Madariaga J.M., 2016b. The cauliflower-like black crusts on sandstones: A natural
331 passive sampler to evaluate the surrounding environmental pollution, *Environ. Res.* 147,
332 218-232.

333 Morillas, H., García-Galan, J., Maguregui, M., García-Florentino, C., Marcaida, I.,
334 Carrero, J.A., Madariaga, J.M., 2016c. In-situ multianalytical methodology to evaluate
335 the conservation state of the entrance arch of La Galea Fortress (Getxo, north of Spain),
336 *Microchem. J.* 128, 288-296.

337 Morillas, H., García-Galán, J., Maguregui, M., Marcaida, I., García-Florentino, C.,
338 Carrero, J.A., Madariaga, J.M., 2016d. Assessment of marine and urban-industrial
339 environments influence on built heritage sandstone using X-ray fluorescence
340 spectroscopy and complementary techniques, *Spectrochim. Acta B.* 123, 76-88.

341 Morillas, H., Marcaida, I., Maguregui, M., Carrero, J.A., Madariaga, J.M., 2016e. The
342 influence of rainwater composition on the conservation state of cementitious building
343 materials, *Sci. Total Environ.* 542, 716-727.

344 O'Dowd, C.D., Lowe, J.A., Smith, M.H., 1999a. Coupling sea-salt and sulphate
345 interactions and its impact on predicting cloud droplet concentrations, *Geophysical
346 Research Letters.* 26, 1311-1314.

347 O'Dowd, C.D., Lowe, J.A., Smith, M.H., Kaye, A.D., 1999b. The relative importance
348 of sea-salt and nss-sulphate aerosol to the marine CCN population: an improved multi-
349 component aerosol-droplet parameterization, *Quarterly Journal of the Royal
350 Meteorological Society.* 125, 1295-1313.

351 O'Dowd, C.D., Lowe, J.A., Clegg, N., Clegg, S.L., Smith, M.H., 2000. Modelling
352 heterogeneous sulphate production in maritime stratiform clouds, *Journal of
353 Geophysical Research.* 105, 7143-7160.

354 O'Dowd, C.D., Hämeri, K., Mäkela, J.M., Pirjola, L., Kulmala, M., Jennings, S.G.,
355 Berresheim, H., Hansson, H.C., de Leeuw, G., Kunz, G.J., Allen, A.G., Hewitt, C.N.,
356 Jackson, A., Viisanen, Y., Hoffmann, T., 2002. A dedicated study of new particle
357 formation and fate in the coastal environment (PARFORCE): overview of objectives
358 and initial achievements, *Journal of Geophysical Research.* 107, 8108.

359 O'Dowd, C.D., de Leeuw, G., 2007. Marine aerosol production: a review of the current
360 knowledge, *Philosophical Transactions of Royal Society A.* 365, 1753-1774.

361 Rodriguez-Navarro, C., Doehne, E., Sebastian, E., 1999. Origins of honeycomb
362 weathering: The role of salts and wind, *GSA Bulletin.* 111, 1250-1255.

363 Sørensen, L.L., Pryor, S., de Leeuw, G., Schulz, M., 2005. Flux divergence for nitric
364 acid in the marine atmospheric surface layer, *Journal of Geophysical Research.* 110,
365 D15306.

366 Tervahattu, H., Juhanoja, J., Vaida, V., Tuck, A.F., Niemi, J.V., Kupiainen, K.,
367 Kulmala, M., Vehkamäki, H., 2005. Fatty acids on continental sulfate aerosol particles,
368 *Journal of Geophysical Research-Atmospheric.* 110, 1984-1991.

369 Textor, C., Schulz, M., Guibert, S., Kinne, S., Balkanski, Y., Bauer, S., Berntsen, T.,
 370 Berglen, T., Boucher, O., Chin, M., Dentener, F., Diehl, T., Easter, R., Feichter, H.,
 371 Fillmore, D., Ghan, S., Ginoux, P., Gong, S., Kristjansson, J.E., Krol, M., Lauer, A.,
 372 Lamarque, J.F., Liu, X., Montanaro, V., Myhre, G., Penner, J., Pitari, G., Reddy, S.,
 373 Seland, O., Stier, P., Takemura, T., Tie, X., 2006. Analysis and quantification of the
 374 diversities of aerosol life cycles within AeroCom, Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics.
 375 6, 1777-1813.

376 Vogt, R., Crutzen, P.J., Sander, R., 1996. A mechanism for halogen release from sea
 377 salt aerosol in the remote marine boundary layer, Nature. 383, 327-330.

378 Zhao, Y., Gao, Y., 2008. Acidic species and chloride depletion in coarse aerosol
 379 particles in the US east coast, Science of the Total Environment. 407, 541-547.

380

381 Figure 1 Fig. 1. a) Scheme of the Punta Begoña Galleries sampling and b) self-made
 382 passive sampler (SMPS) scheme.

383

384

385 Figure. 2. SEM-EDS imaging showing in all the figures the major presence of Na and
 386 Cl and around them A) and B) Ca, S and O (calcium sulfates presence) and Mg, K, and
 387 Si (aluminosilicates and sulfates presence) distributions; C) N and O (possible nitrates
 388 presence) distributions and D) P and F distributions (possible phosphate and fluoride
 389 presence).

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391 Figure 3. Process of formation of the mixed sulfate-chloride NaCaClSO_4 showing the
 392 different reaction steps that lead to its formation starting from A) halite (NaCl) and B)
 393 calcium sulfate (anhydrite, CaSO_4 and/or gypsum, $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$); C) intermediate salt
 394 cluster formation and D) final NaCaClSO_4 formation.

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 396 Figure 4. Different SEM-EDS results of salt clusters composed by A) Ca, Na, S and O
 397 (possible glauberite NaCaSO_4) of diameter size up to 30 μm, B) aluminosilicates and
 398 iron oxides added to possible glauberite with diameter size up to 60 μm and C) Na and
 399 Cl (halite, NaCl) composed salt cluster (diameter size up to 30 μm) which includes
 400 elements such as Al, Si, Fe and Ca.

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Table 1. Raman spectra of the salts-cluster particles

<i>Salts-Cluster particles</i>	<i>Mineral Name</i>	<i>Raman bands ν (cm^{-1})</i>
CaSO_4	Anhydrite type III	420 m, 490m, 630m, 673m, 1025 vs, 1167m.
$\text{Na}_3(\text{SO}_4)(\text{NO}_3)\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Darapskite	472 vw, 619 w, 640 w, 707 w, 729 w, 993 s, 1059 vs, 1084 w, 1122 vw, 1354 w, 1416 w.
$\text{Na}_4\text{Ca}(\text{SO}_4)_3\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Eugsterite	1084 s, 1124 s
$\text{K}_2\text{Ca}(\text{SO}_4)\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Syngenite	441 s, 472 m, 492 w, 603 m, 621 m, 633 m, 642 m, 661 m, 981 vs, 1006 vs, 1082 m, 1119 m, 1139 w, 1165 w.
$\text{K}_2\text{Ca}_2\text{Mg}(\text{SO}_4)_4\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Polyhalite	236 m, 438 m, 465 s, 623 vw, 653 m, 989 vs, 1016 vs, 1071 m, 1093 m, 1131 m, 1165 m.
$\text{CaNa}_2(\text{SO}_4)_2$	Glauberite	453 w, 471 s, 485 m, 619 m, 624 m, 636 m, 644 s, 1001 vs, 1106 w, 1139 s, 1156 m, 1169 m
$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	Mascagnite	449 m, 614 w, 622 w, 974 vs, 1104 vw, 1417 vw.
$\text{CaSO}_4\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Gypsum	413 m, 492 m, 619 m, 673 m, 1008 vs, 1132 m.
K_2SO_4	Arcanite	455 m, 619 m, 988 vs, 1092 w, 1103 w, 1144 vw.
$\text{MgSO}_4\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Hexahydrate	249 w, 361 w, 442 w, 464 vw, 603 w, 982 vs, 1083 vw, 1148 vw.
$\text{MgSO}_4\cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Epsomite	362 vw, 445 w, 462 w, 609 w, 985 vs, 1082 vw, 1145 vw.
Na_2SO_4	Thenardite	450 w, 465 w, 621 m, 632 m, 647 m, 992 vs, 1101 m, 1132 m, 1152 m.
$\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4\cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Mirabilite	446 w, 458 w, 616 m, 628 m, 989 vs, 1108 m, 1120 m, 1130m.
NaNO_3	Nitratine	188 m, 414 vw, 518 vw, 533 vw, 722 s, 1067 vs, 1383 w, 1663 vw, 1775 vw.
$\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	Nitromagnesite	729 s, 1059 vs, 1359 m, 1432 w.